

Apical Debris Extrusion of Two Heat Treated Rotary NiTi Instruments; AF F-One Files and Orodeka Plex-V Files in Severe Curved Simulated Canals. A Comparative *In Vitro* Study

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Abstract

Objective: the extrusion of apical debris is considered as the prime reasons of endodontic flare up. The aim of this paper was to calculate the weight of this debris after preparation of curved resin canals using two different endodontic rotary systems: Fanta AF F-One and Orodeka Plex-V files.

Materials and methods: twenty curved simulated resin canals were divided into two sets (n=10) rendering to the files applied for canal instrumentation. All samples were prepared with apical file of 25/04. The debris was to be collected in pre-weighed vials then incubated at 37°C for two weeks. Then the vials were re weighing and the quantity of debris of each canal was collected from subtracting the amount of pre-weight from post-weight of the vial. t-test was utilized to compare the mean weight of the extrusion to assess the significant difference between the examined groups. Level of significance was 0.05.

Results: there was no significant difference between the tested groups in term of apically extruded debris (P=0.724). Plex-V system showed more percent of extrusion than AF F-One system.

Conclusions: the two tested systems extruded debris without significant difference.

List of Abbreviations: Nickle-titanium (NiTi), Apical Extruded Debris (AED), Root canal treatment (RCT), Working length (WL), rotation per minute (rpm), Newton (N), Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS), Probability value (P). Significant (Sig), That is to say (i.e.,).

Introduction

The objective of root canal debridement is to eliminate the pulp tissue and microorganism and their byproducts out of the root system. It also provides adequate space for irrigations, intracanal medicaments, and obturating materials [1]. Even with the controlled working length during preparation, undesirable extrusion of pulp tissues, dentin chips, microbes, and chemicals may pass out to the periapical area [2].

Meanwhile preparation of the root system, the apically extruded debris (AED) is the primary reason of root canal failure [3]. AED considered as the main reason of postoperative pain and flare-up following root canal treatment (RCT) [4]. AED is multifactorial etiology, and it may be associated to teeth-attributed factors, instrumentation techniques as well as irrigation

delivery systems. Additionally, instruments significantly affect AED [5].

Several articles have shown that all root canal preparation techniques were associated with AED, however, the quantity of AED differs among the different file systems [5]. The geometry of the file, cutting efficiency in addition to the number of files used may affect the volume of AED [6].

In the paper at hand, demonstrative files of rotary NiTi instruments, AF F-One and Orodeka Plex-V files, were designated as the experimental objects.

More recently, a heat treated NiTi rotary file, AF F-One (Fanta, Shanghai, China), with flat-side design was introduced to reduce blade engagement and to improve cyclic fatigue resistance, as well as eliminating the debris out of the root canal. The file intended with S-shaped cross-section figure is categorized as a non-

More Information

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apical extrusion, debris, Fanta AF F-One, Orodeka Plex-V.

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cutting tip and double active cutting edges. Furthermore, it presents a new heat treatment named AF-R wire. As stated by the internal studies of manufacture, this heat treatment should improve cutting efficiency and provide an advanced torsional and cyclic fatigue resistance other than NiTi instruments [7].

Orodeka Plex-V system (Shandong Province, China) is a recently introduced file system with a continuous rotation motion manufactured from the newly alloy of NiTi CM wire as special thermal treatment. It aims at improving the resistance to cyclic fatigue and the flexibility of triangular cross-section file, which is designed to facilitate the removal of root canal contents and minimize the contact with the root canal walls. The tip of the file is non-active without blades, and it has no cutting function but only for negotiation to avoid the ledges formation and/or perforations along the root canal walls [8].

An extensive literature search showed that there is no research considering the quantity of AED using the F-One compared to Plex-V files, hence this was the objective of the present *in vitro* study.

Materials and Methods

Simulated Canals

In the present study, 20 simulated, transparent J-shaped resin blocks root canals (Dentsply Maillefer, Ballaigues, Switzerland) were used. The taper and width of the artificial blocks were equal to an ISO K-file size 10. The working length (WL) of the canal was 16mm long, the straight part being 11mm and the curved part 5mm. The curvature was 45° in line with Schneider [9], resulting in radius of 5.5mm according to Pruett *et al.*, [10].

Collecting and Weighing Model for AED

Present study used the experimental model designated by Myers and Montgomery [11] to weight AED. 10 ml glass vial (Baghdad factory, Iraq), was weighted without the plastic cover by an electrical balance (accuracy:10⁻⁴ g). Each vial was weighted 3 times, and the average value was considered as the original weight of the vial. A slot was perforated in the midpoint of the plastic cover, then the artificial canal was secure into this slot. The gap was sealed using cyanoacrylate resin (Al-Mansur, Iraq) to prevent the unintentional leakage of the irrigating solution. Then, the separated cover with the resin block were fitted over the pre-weighted vial. Needle gauge 23 (Samara, Iraq) was inserted to equilibrium the pressure in and out of the vial (fig.1). Then, the vial was covered with a rubber dam (Sanctuary Health SDN BHD, Malaysia) to ensure that the operator cannot observe the resin canal as well as the extrusion of debris throughout root canal preparation.

Figure 1: Apparatus of Debris Collection

Preparation of Artificial Canals

The samples were divided into two experimental groups (n=10) according to the files used in root canal instrumentation. The preparation was accomplished by a single operator, specialist in endodontics and experienced in preparation with both rotary systems which were used in this study and driven by the X-Smart Plus iQ electric motor (Dentsply, Maillefer, Ballaigues, Switzerland). K-file size 10 was used along the simulated root canal to reach patency. The blocks were prepared with sequence files according to the manufacturer's orders. The irrigating fluid, distilled water (Al-Mansur factory, Iraq) was delivered with a 30-gauge, disposable side-vented tip and 21mm needle (UltraDent Products, Inc., South Jordan, UT, USA). The needle tip was inserted passively about 2mm from the WL. The irrigant fluid was delivered slowly inside the canal and the canal was washed with 2ml of distilled water after the removal of each file out of the canal.

Group1: in this group, the resin canals were instrumented by AF F-One rotary files (Fanta Dental Materials Co., Shanghai, China) (fig.2), driven by X-Smart Plus electric motor, at a pre-programmed movement format as "AF rotary system" mode.

1. Orifice opener (17/12), WL: 5mm, speed: 500rpm, torque: 2.5 N
2. Path finder (16/04), WL: 15mm, speed: 500rpm, torque: 2 N
3. Shaping file with yellow ring (20/04), WL: 15mm, speed: 500rpm, torque: 2.5 N
4. Finishing file with red ring (25/04), WL: 15mm, speed: 500rpm, torque: 2.5 N

Figure 2: AF F-One File. Notice the Flat Side of the File

Group2: this group was prepared by Orodeka Plex-V system (Shandong Province, China). The X-Smart Plus electric motor was pre-programmed motion according to the manufacturer’s recommendations regarding speed and torque.

1. Orifice Opener (15/08), WL:5mm, speed:500rpm, torque: 2.5 N
2. Glide Path (15/03), WL: 15mm, speed: 300rpm, torque: 1.5 N
3. Shaping file with yellow ring (20/04), WL: 15mm, speed: 500rpm, torque: 2.5 N
4. Shaping file red ring (25/04), WL: 15mm, speed: 500rpm, torque: 2.5 N

All instruments were moved in a slow in and out pecking motion advancing approximately 2-3mm. As soon as the movement of the file was constrained, the file was instantly pulled out of the canal, and the duration of file rotation was no more than 5 seconds.

The rotary file was removed as soon as it had been rotated freely and negotiated to the end of the canal. After replacement or withdrawal, the file was disinfected by a piece of cotton saturated with 75% alcohol. After irrigation, canal was recapped via K-file size 10. Afterward, the debris adhered to the apex of the canal was collected by rinsing the apex in the vial with 2ml distilled water. In other words, 12ml distilled water was used in the process for each canal. During each root canal instrumentation, files were inspected for any deformations or cracks and were immediately replaced as any are detected.

Collecting and Re-Weighing Debris

After removal of the artificial canal-cover assembly, vials were incubated at 37°C for two weeks to facilitate the evaporation of water, leaving just the extruded materials. For re-weighing, the vials were transferred to the electronic balance and weighted 3 times for an accurate final average. The final weight of extruded debris was calculated by subtracting the values of pre-weight from post-weight of the vial.

Data Analysis

The outcomes obtained were analyzed statistically by t-test using SPSS version 26 (SPSS Inc., Chicago, IL, USA). The level of significance was set at P<0.05.

Results

Given the findings of this study, both groups exhibited debris extrusion with various values. The outcomes of the descriptive statistics of AED for the two groups are shown in table 1 and figure 3.

Table 1: Statistics Description of AED (gram) of the Tested Groups

Groups	Mean	Minimum	Maximum	Standard deviation
Group 1 (F-One)	0.00111	0.0003	0.0025	.000740
Group 2 (Plex V)	0.00122	0.0004	0.0023	.000625

Figure 3: Bar Chart Showing the Weight of Debris Extrusion in Gram

According to table 1 and figure 3, F-One system extruded less debris (0.00111±.000740) than Plex-V system (0.00122±.000625).

Inferential statistic was performed with t-test (table 2), which showed that there was no significant difference between the two groups (P=0.724).

Table 2: Intergroup Comparison between Weight of Debris Using t-Test.

t	Sig.	Mean Difference	Standard Errors
.359	.724	.00011	.0003063

Discussion

Throughout RCT, the precisely measured working length does not prevent the extrusion of the undesirable intracanal contents to the periapical area, i.e., dentin chips, pulp tissues, irrigating solutions, microorganisms, and intracanal medicaments. The AED may cause postoperative pain, inflammation, flare-up, and interfere with the healing of periapical tissues [2,12]. The prevalence of such complications has been stated to be about 1.4%-16% in the literature review [12]. According to the scientific basis, all preparation procedures and instrument systems may force root canal debris into the periapical area [13].

AED is a multifactorial complication, and it may be assigned to tooth-associated reasons i.e., tooth type, root curvature, apical foramen size, and the age of the patient. Furthermore, files meaningfully affect AED, including geometry, metal, kinematics, and the numbers of files have been used. Additionally, instrumentation techniques, the amount and delivery systems of irrigation into the canal have been recognized to perform an important part in discharge root canal contents to the periapical area [5].

Throughout preparation of root canal, a reduction in AED is necessary to minimize the postoperative pain after RCT [14,15]. AED has been recognized as a crucial factor in clinical parameter for evaluating the efficacy of preparation procedures along with the files that have been used. Selecting root canal preparation instruments that cause the least amount of AED improve the success rate of RCT. Consequently, multiple studies have emphasized the importance of examining this parameter when assessing the clinical performance of recently developed endodontic files [16].

In investigating the performance of NiTi files, extracted teeth were mostly applied as examination samples. Due to the specific differences, it seems difficult to standardize the size of apical foramen, dentin hardness, and the anatomy of the extracted teeth; hence, the model's standardization is minimal, and the reference value of the investigational results is limited. On the other hand, the consistency of simulated resin canals is outstanding, nearly the same root canal morphology, angle, radius of curvature and length of canal are attained, that may efficiently minimize the experimental errors [17]. Throughout the instrumentation of the simulated canal, the hardness of resin block was not significantly different from that of the natural dentin and there were no complications, such as resin softening or file fracture [17].

Several studies [18,19,20] have stated that, 3D-printed models can progressively replace extracted teeth and serve as new samples for assessing the performance of root canal instrumentation systems. Along with the same line, Yu *et al.* [21] used artificial canals to evaluate the AED produced by various NiTi instruments. Hence, in study at hands, the simulated root canals were used as models to methodically investigate the tested instruments. This is accepted to provide a reference and investigational basis for the preferred choice of instrumentation files in RCT, particularly in curved root. The Myers and Montgomery technique for the assessment of AED was utilized in this research due to its competency, simplicity, and precise measurements. To demonstrate the efficiency of this technique, the impact of touching the equipment with wet hands or even environmental contamination may significantly affect the final results [5].

During the irrigation of the root system, AED can be pushed into the periradicular tissue [5]. Therefore, in this study, the delivery of irrigant solutions was applied passively. And to avoid operator variations, one operator prepared the entire procedures. Each resin block was instrumented by a new set of files to guarantee that wear of instrument had no effect over extrusion of debris.

The results of this study presented that the F-One files produced less quantity of AED than Plex-V files, with no significant differences between the two tested instruments. These data can be related to the reduced metal mass of F-One file.

Regarding the reduction of metal mass, the flat design, as a characteristic feature of F-One file, minimizes the core of instrument. Consequently, it maximizes the space for sweeping the debris and irrigation from the flutes to the relieved area [22]. This explanation agreed with Schafer *et al.* (2006) who stated that, the flat side contributes to create a greater space between the file and canal walls, permitting for more debris collection and capacity removal [23]. Additionally, Bürklein *et al.* (2012) reveals that, the reduced chip space of a file, the lesser its escape area and subsequently its debris removal capacity [24].

Another geometric property of the instrument that may contribute to clarifying the result of this study, is the cross-section of the instrument. According to a systematic review by Caviedes-Bucheli (2016), the design of cross-section related to the rotary instrument is significantly influencing the amount of AED more than the kinematics of the file [25]. F-One files is reported to have S-shaped cross-section and slightly positive rake angle in combination with radial land relief [26]. On the other side, Plex-V file is presented by a modified triangular cross-section resulting in smaller chip space [24].

Similarly, Walsch (2004) revealed that, a positive rake angle improved the dentin cutting and the elimination of debris from the root canal. Dentin chips resulting from the file with positive rake angle are easily dislodged from the pulp system and removed coronally by its unique helical angle [27].

In this study the clarifications mentioned act as a compelling explanation of the variations in debris extrusion among the tested systems.

Conclusions

It can be observed that in the present *in vitro* study. Both types of examined instruments produced AED. AF F-one system extruded less amounts of AED in comparison with Ordeka Plex-V systems without significant differences between the two groups. These results confirm that less metal mass means more space to collect and coronal evacuation of the intracanal debris.

Conflict of interest

Authors have nothing to declare.

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